

EMI-Silent Operation of Triple Active Bridge Converters with Online Model-Free ZVS Optimization and RMS Current Reduction

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Abstract—Triple active bridge (TAB) converter, an isolated multi-port converter (IMPC), connects three dc ports via a three-terminal high-frequency transformer, enabling zero voltage switching (ZVS) without the need for additional snubber circuits. However, under certain loading conditions ZVS is lost and rms currents increase. This paper introduces a model-free, online optimization method using multi-dimensional ripple correlation control (MD-RCC) to ensure ZVS operation while reducing rms currents. The MD-RCC is an online model-free approach, providing robust performance against parameter uncertainties or operational variations. Two distinct methods are utilized to evaluate the cost function online. The first method involves the oversampling of the transformer currents. The second approach relies on the correlation between the EMI noise level and the hard switching of the devices, providing a simpler alternative to oversampling techniques. The proposed MD-RCC technique has been validated through both simulation and experimental testing on a 5 kW prototype, demonstrating its efficacy in optimizing ZVS, reducing EMI noise, and rms currents.

Index Terms—Triple active bridge (TAB), multi-dimensional ripple correlation control (MD-RCC), zero voltage switching (ZVS), EMI noise, rms current optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Isolated multi-port converters (IMPCs) offer high efficiency, power density, and galvanic isolation by utilizing multi-terminal high-frequency transformers (HFTs) to interface ports with varying voltage or current ratings [1]–[3]. They are widely used in applications such as DC microgrids [4], [5], electric aircraft [6]–[8], and electric vehicles [9]–[13]. The triple active bridge converter (TAB), displayed in Fig. 1 [14], is an IMPC with three ports, and it can be

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Fig. 1: Triple active bridge converter (TAB). The current direction is arbitrary and may be adjusted according to the specific application and modeling requirements.

considered as an extension to an additional port of the dual active bridge (DAB) [15]. TAB comprises a three-terminal HFT connected to three bridges [14]. The HFT plays a crucial role in interfacing the dc ports and allowing a controlled energy transfer path through its leakage inductances L_1 , L_2 , and L_3 [14].

Phase shift modulation (PSM), represented in Fig. 2(a), can be utilized to control the power flow of TABs. In this scheme, the transformer terminal voltages v_1 , v_2 , and v_3 are considered, where v_1 serves as the reference. PSM concerns the definition of the external phase shifts ϕ_2 and ϕ_3 of the generated ac voltages v_2 and v_3 . PSM is a straightforward modulation scheme featuring low conduction losses and the capability to achieve zero voltage switching (ZVS) in nominal operating conditions [14]. However, PSM operation may significantly depart from the optimal condition, where high losses emerge at low power transfer or when the dc ports

voltage ratios are not matched with the transformer turns ratio, i.e., $V_2/V_1 \neq n_2/n_1$ and $V_3/V_1 \neq n_3/n_1$ [14].

Multiphase-shift modulation (MPSM), shown in Fig. 2(b), was introduced to overcome PSM limitations by exploiting internal phase shifts, namely the duty-cycles D_1, D_2 , and D_3 of the voltages v_1, v_2 , and v_3 , respectively [14]. MPSM allows tuning TAB operation by adjusting these duty-cycles aiming at operating points with reduced rms and full ZVS operation.

While optimizing the operating efficiency is a renowned fundamental objective [14], [16]–[24], securing ZVS operation throughout the entire range of operation also presents remarkable advantages, including those outlined next. *i)* Reduced EMI: ZVS ensures, by definition, soft switching transitions, which are associated with lower generated electromagnetic noise [25]–[27]. *ii)* Improved reliability and power density: Reduced switching loss means that devices are subjected to less thermal stress, improving switch reliability and optimizing heatsink size. Additionally, ZVS helps prevent undesired voltage ringings, which is also associated with reduced component stresses and overall better reliability [28]. *iii)* Enhanced efficiency at high switching frequencies: the utilization of wide-bandgap semiconductors (i.e., SiC, GaN) elevates the switching frequency, reducing the size of the passives. However, switching losses have higher impacts at higher switching frequencies. ZVS reduces turn-on losses of the switches, which is a significant part of the switching loss [29], [30] *iv)* Lessen snubber circuits requirements: TAB operation can be exploited to achieve ZVS over the whole operating range by a proper modulation scheme, without the need for external snubber circuits [29].

ZVS conditions for TABs have been explored in several works. In [16], a ZVS criterion considering all TAB parameters was introduced but ignored conduction losses. [17] proposed a universal analytical model using frequency-domain analysis and particle swarm optimization to minimize RMS current while ensuring ZVS. Similarly, [31] employed a generalized harmonic approximation (GHA) to model TAB operation, focusing on ZVS and switching loss reduction but overlooking conduction loss minimization. Despite their effectiveness, the optimizations in [16], [17], and [31] rely on complex analytical models and predefined look-up tables, limiting adaptability to real hardware and operating conditions. Alternatively, [32] introduced an online optimization approach for minimizing switching losses using time-domain ZVS equations. However, despite being online, it still relies on intricate models and lacks adaptability to parameter variations during operation.

This paper proposes a model-free online optimization method for the TAB converter based on multi-dimensional ripple correlation control (MD-RCC). While MD-RCC has been previously applied to optimize the rms current of TAB converters [24] and improve the efficiency of quadruple active bridge (QAB) converters [33], this work utilizes MD-RCC concepts to optimize ZVS operation with reduced rms currents. Hence, the thermal stresses of the switches and the converter efficiency are improved, besides a reduction in the EMI noise level emitted by the converter [27]. The

Fig. 2: Switching sequence of TAB modulation schemes: (a) phase-shift modulation (PSM); (b) multiphase-shift modulation (MPSM).

proposed method offers both online and model-free advantages, enabling online adaptation to parameter variations, such as resistance, inductance, deadtime, and switching frequency, etc. The paper addresses the challenges of modeling ZVS operation online and presents two distinct methods for achieving optimization.

The first method involves oversampling the transformer current, followed by capturing the switching current and integrating it into the cost function. The second method utilizes the correlation between the hard switching current and the EMI noise levels, using an analog circuit to catch a representation of the EMI noise. This method is a simpler alternative to oversampling techniques, providing equivalent experimental results. Notably, the proposed optimization aims to optimize the performance of all three active bridges simultaneously.

The paper is an extended version of the work originally presented in [34], with the following additional contributions:

- Presenting in detail the cost function proposed in [34], and how to implement it online.
- Proposing a simpler alternative to the cost function in [34], utilizing an analogue circuit instead of complex oversampling techniques.
- Introducing comprehensive experimental data comparing the effect of using different cost functions on the overall performance of the converter.

The paper is organized into six sections. The introduction section defines the problem of TAB optimization. Sect. II discusses optimal modulation of TAB utilizing MPSM. Sect. III proposes MD-RCC optimizing different cost functions. Sect. IV introduces a novel cost function, optimizing EMI noise. While Sect. V details the experimental prototype and explains how the proposed cost functions are evaluated online. Finally, Sect. VI concludes the paper.

II. OPTIMAL MODULATION OF TAB CONVERTERS

PSM is a straightforward modulation scheme employed to regulate the power flow in TABs, as shown in Fig. 2(a).

By the PSM, the external phase shifts, ϕ_2 and ϕ_3 , between the three bridges, considering the first bridge as a reference, are adjusted to control the power flow, directing it from the leading to the lagging port, with the theoretical maximum at a phase shift of $\pi/2$ [14]. The external phase shift ϕ_2 represents the displacement between the switching of S_1 and S_5 , likewise ϕ_3 is the shift between S_1 and S_9 , as shown in Fig. 2(a). However, PSM leads to high losses, especially with low transferred power and mismatches among the ports voltage ratios and the transformer turns ratio. This typically brings increased rms current, increased joule losses, as well as loss of ZVS. Instead, by MPSM, the internal phase shift between two legs within a full bridge is controlled beside the external phase shifts in order to alleviate the issue [14]. The internal phase shift for each bridge is represented by the duty-cycle of the corresponding bridge, namely, D_1, D_2 , and D_3 for the three bridges, as shown in Fig. 2(b). The internal phase shift represents the shift between the switching instances of S_1 and S_4 for port-1, controlling D_1 , as shown in Fig. 2(b); the same is applied to port-2 and port-3.

A. Optimizing MPSM for Minimum rms Current

Controlling the internal phase shift of each full bridge enables regulation of the generated voltage duty-cycles, as shown in Fig. 2(b). In this way, three degrees of freedom, namely, D_1, D_2 , and D_3 , are utilized to enhance TAB operation. In [21]–[24], the pursuit of minimizing the joule losses involves reducing the rms currents flowing through the converter, pursued herein by the measure (1).

$$i^{rms} = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^3 i_{k,rms}^2}, \quad k = 1, 2, 3 \quad (1)$$

where, i_{rms} is the total rms current, k denotes the port number, and i_k is the corresponding port rms current. To show the effectiveness of MPSM over PSM, a grid search optimization (GSO) is carried out to determine the optimum duty-cycles (i.e., D_1, D_2 , and D_3) for minimum total rms current. The GSO systematically explores all possible combinations of duty-cycles for a TAB converter with parameters outlined in Table I, using a PLECS simulation. Meanwhile, the phase shifts (i.e., ϕ_2 and ϕ_3) are adjusted using a pair of regulators to control the power exchange at port-2 and port-3. The simulation is designed to consider various loading conditions. Port-1 and 2 voltages remain constant at their rated values, while port-3 voltage varies from 0.6 to 1.4 the rated voltage. In this setup, the power flows from port-1 to ports-2 and 3. Port-2 power is constant at 100 W, while port-3 power changes from 100 W to the rated power. The GSO is employed with a resolution step of 0.05 on the duty-cycles. The resolution step is chosen iteratively, starting with a larger step size and gradually reducing it until the identified minimum points show minimal variation with further refinement.

Fig. 3 illustrates total rms current of PSM and GSO, besides the corresponding ZVS performance as detailed in Sect. II-B. Fig. 3(a) illustrates the rms current for PSM, while Fig. 3(b)

Fig. 3: Simulation results of TAB; (a)-(b) total rms current for phase-shift modulation (PSM) and grid search optimization (GSO), respectively; (c)-(d) percentage of devices achieving ZVS ($N_{\%}^{ZVS}$) for PSM and GSO, respectively. Converter parameters as in Table I.

presents the rms current for GSO under the same operating conditions. As shown in Fig. 3(b), GSO achieves a significant reduction in rms current compared to PSM. The recorded reductions score up to 80% of the original value with the PSM. Such a substantial decrease in total rms current is particularly valuable in scenarios of low-power operation with voltage mismatch.

B. Optimizing MPSM for Enhanced ZVS and Reduced rms Current

To compare the effectiveness of different modulation schemes in achieving ZVS, criteria to discern ZVS should be defined first. As detailed in [35], the criteria used herein is based on the computation of the minimum threshold current i_{th} necessary to discharge the parasitic capacitance C_{eq} of a switching device initially operating at voltage V_{ds} , assuming a fixed discharge current during a given available deadtime $t_{deadtime}$:

$$i_{th} = \frac{2V_{ds}C_{eq}}{t_{deadtime}} \quad (2)$$

For example, considering the parameters in Table I, the calculated threshold current is 400 mA. For a single leg comprising two switches, namely S_1 and S_2 , as illustrated in Fig. 1, with current and voltage directions indicated, the ZVS conditions are as follows.

- 1) The upper switch S_1 achieves full ZVS if the turn-on current $i_{S1_{on}}$ is less than the negative threshold value, that is, $i_{S1_{on}} < -i_{th}$.

Fig. 4: Total rms current, defined in (1), and number of hard switching devices, out of the total 12 devices, resulting in each GSO iteration.

- 2) The lower switch S_2 achieves full ZVS if the turn-on current i_{S2_on} is greater than the positive threshold value, that is, $i_{S2_on} > +i_{th}$.

Based on these conditions, the percentage of devices satisfying the ZVS criteria is assessed and referred to as $N_{\%}^{ZVS}$ in (3).

$$N_{\%}^{ZVS} = \frac{N_{ZVS}}{N_{total}} * 100 \quad (3)$$

where N_{ZVS} is the number of switches experiencing zero-voltage switching at turn on, while N_{total} is the total number of converter switches, namely, 12 for the TAB. The results are illustrated in Fig. 3(c) for PSM and in Fig. 3(d) for GSO referring to (1). It is worth noting that the GSO objective is exclusively to identify points with the lowest rms current, regardless of ZVS conditions. Consequently, the attained ZVS profiles are incidental.

To show that operation with all transitions in ZVS can be reached with MPSM, the GSO is modified to search for minimum rms current restricted within the subset in which full or partial ZVS is realized. Fig. 4 displays the GSO iterations for the test case in Fig. 3 with port-3 power at 100 W and port-3 voltage at 240 V. For the GSO aiming to minimize the rms current only, iteration #2 gives the best outcome, yielding a total rms current of 2.17 A with six devices in hard-switching, that is, $N_{\%}^{ZVS} = 50\%$. Differently, when integrating ZVS as a requirement for GSO solutions, iteration #95 yields a total rms current of 3.26 A with zero hard switching devices, namely achieving 100% ZVS.

Noticeably, pursuing minimum rms current within a subset featuring all the transitions in ZVS might lead to an increase in the total rms current. However, this outcome is also dependent on the GSO resolution step: a finer step could potentially identify better solutions with lower rms currents. Additionally, even with the modified GSO, the obtained rms current still demonstrates a significant reduction as compared to the PSM marked at approximately 11 A. Notably, a well-defined cost function that accounts for both the total rms current and ZVS operation can be used to optimize converter performance, as detailed in Sect. III-A.

Fig. 5: Multi-dimensional ripple correlation search (MD-RCC), optimizing cost function in (5).

III. ONLINE MODEL-FREE OPTIMIZATION OF TAB

In Sect. II, MPSM shows the ability to attain full or partial ZVS and reduce the flowing rms currents. However, the employed GSO exhibits drawbacks, including a substantial time requirement for data collection, a significant computational burden with a small resolution step, and the necessity to store results in look-up tables. Additionally, the GSO lacks the adaptability to accommodate parameter changes in the converter resulting from variations in operating conditions. Hence, an online model-free optimization method has been implemented to optimize the performance of the TAB with full or partial ZVS operation and with reduced rms currents. The optimization approach utilized herein is known as multi-dimensional ripple correlation control (MD-RCC), initially introduced in [24] to optimize the rms current of the TAB converter and in [33] to optimize the efficiency of the quadruple active bridge (QAB). However, its application to optimize the ZVS operation of TAB has not been explored previously.

MD-RCC is based on the operating principle of the ripple correlation control (RCC), also known as extremum-seeking control (ESC) [36]. In RCC, the optimization of a specific cost function involves imposing a perturbation on the control variable. The correlation between the applied perturbation and the cost function is then identified. Subsequently, the control variable is adjusted, guided by the estimated correlation, in the direction of either maximizing or minimizing the cost function.

To optimize a given cost function with multiple degrees of freedom, corresponding perturbations are superimposed on the control variables, herein duty-cycles D_1, D_2 , and D_3 . These perturbations must possess distinct frequencies. This allows for independently measuring the correlation between the cost function and each perturbation, thanks to the orthogonality among the perturbations and the corresponding effects. The imposed perturbations can be defined as

$$\epsilon \sin \omega_k t, \quad k = 1, 2, 3 \quad (4)$$

where, ϵ is the perturbation magnitude and ω_k is the corresponding perturbation frequency at port- k .

Fig. 5 shows the implementation of MD-RCC. The low-pass filters (LPF) serve as an approximation of a moving average. Consequently, these filters should be designed with a cutoff frequency sufficiently lower than the minimum perturbation frequency to ensure accurate averaging within each perturbation cycle. Additionally, the stability considerations in [24] must be considered:

- 1) The maximum perturbation frequency should be much slower than the plant dynamics (i.e., the plant is considered as a static map w.r.t the maximum correlation perturbation).
- 2) The perturbation frequencies should be different to guarantee orthogonality.
- 3) The low pass filters should have a cutoff frequency lower than the lowest difference between the perturbation frequencies.
- 4) The perturbation magnitude should have a very small value compared to the possible optimum (e.g., 1% of full duty-cycle).

A. Optimizing Switches Turn-on Current with Reduced rms

To simultaneously maintain low rms currents and optimize ZVS operation, a novel cost function is introduced herein:

$$I_{ZVS}^{rms} = K_{rms} \cdot i^{rms} + K_{ZVS} \cdot I_{HS} \quad (5)$$

$$I_{HS} = \sqrt{\sum_{m=1}^{m_{device}} H_m I_{m,HS}^2} \quad (6)$$

where, K_{rms} and K_{ZVS} are weighting factors, i^{rms} is the total rms current as defined in (1), m is the number of switches ($m = 1, \dots, 12$), H_m indicates whether the m -th device is hard or soft switching, specifically, $H_m = 1$ for hard switching devices (i.e., ZVS criteria in (2) are not met), $H_m = 0$ for soft switching devices, and $I_{m,HS}$ denotes the switched current at the switching instant.

The weighting factors K_{rms} and K_{ZVS} are adjustable parameters designed to achieve ZVS while minimizing rms current. The selection of the weighting parameters depends on the optimization objectives of the cost function. For instance, if $K_{rms} \gg K_{ZVS}$, the priority shifts toward minimizing rms current over achieving full ZVS operation, and vice-versa. Therefore, a balance between these weighting factors is essential and can be attained through iterative tuning.

The online computational procedure of (5) is shown in Fig. 6. The cost function includes the overall rms current of the TAB, combined with the hard switching commutation currents.

B. Simulation Results

To evaluate the effectiveness of the defined cost function (5), the MD-RCC-based approach was first implemented in a simulation model using PLECS, with parameters listed in Table I. The test scenario in Sect. II was considered to assess the optimization capability of the approach and the defined cost function in achieving ZVS for all the switches over a

Fig. 6: Online implementation of the cost I_{ZVS}^{rms} in (5) for the TAB in Fig. 1; i_{th} calculated with (2); i^{rms} calculated with (1). Hard switching detection, for computing $N_{\%}^{ZVS}$ in (3), is performed considering all the 12 converter switches.

TABLE I: TAB parameters.

Parameters	Value	
Nominal power at each port P_{rated}	kW	5
Switching frequency $f_s = 1/T_s$	kHz	40
Rated dc voltages V_1-V_3	V	400
Transf. turns ratio $n_1 : n_2 : n_3$		1:1:1
Transf. leakage inductances $L_1 - L_3$	μH	44
Switching Devices	Cree C2M0080120D	
Dead time	μs	0.2
Sinusoidal perturbation magnitude ϵ		0.0025
Weights $K_{rms}, K_{ZVS}, K_{EMI}$		5, 10, 20
Perturbation frequencies $\omega_1 - \omega_3$	rad/s	$10\pi, 14\pi, 18\pi$,
LPF cutoff frequency ω_c	rad/s	4π

comprehensive set of operating conditions. For each combination of port-3 power and voltage, the MD-RCC is executed to minimize the proposed cost function (5), which takes into account both total rms current and the hard switching currents if ZVS criteria defined in Sect. II-B are not satisfied. This process steers the converter operation away from unfavorable operating conditions for ZVS while sliding towards operating points with low rms currents.

Fig. 7 shows the results of applying the MD-RCC considering the minimization of the total rms current i^{rms} (1) versus the proposed cost function I_{ZVS}^{rms} (5). As compared to rms currents minimization displayed in Fig. 7(a), the use of the proposed cost function leads to approximately equivalent rms currents in Fig. 7(b). However, by the proposed cost function, nearly all the switches satisfy the ZVS criterion, as shown in Fig. 7(d). This desirable result is not achieved using (1), as shown in Fig. 7(c), because such a cost function disregards switching conditions (i.e., soft or hard switching).

IV. EMI-SILENT OPTIMIZATION WITH REDUCED RMS

Sec. III-B approved the feasibility of achieving a near-by optimum rms current while maintaining the ZVS operation of the converter utilizing (5) as a cost function. While (5) effectively represents the converter losses, it presents significant challenges for online implementation. Specifically, the

Fig. 7: Simulation results of MD-RCC with TAB: (a)-(b) total rms current of MD-RCC optimizing i^{rms} in (1), and I_{ZVS}^{rms} in (4), respectively; (c)-(d) percentage devices achieving ZVS ($N_{\%}^{ZVS}$) of MD-RCC optimizing i^{rms} in (1), and I_{ZVS}^{rms} in (4), respectively.

term $I_{m,HS}$ requires oversampling of the transformer current, which adds complexity and cost to the optimization process.

A simplified cost function that can be fully implemented using analog circuits is proposed in this section. The new cost function leverages the correlation between the hard switching current and the generated EMI noise level. As will be experimentally shown in Sect. V, an increase in hard switching current typically corresponds to a rise in EMI noise. This relationship is exploited by sensing the EMI noise level, as described in Sect. V, and incorporating it into the cost function in place of the term $I_{m,HS}$.

Reducing EMI noise tends to drive the system toward ZVS operation inherently. The newly proposed cost function is presented in (7).

$$I_{EMI}^{rms} = K_{rms} \cdot i^{rms} + K_{EMI} \cdot v^{EMI} \quad (7)$$

$$v^{EMI} = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^3 v_{k,EMI}^2} \quad (8)$$

where K_{EMI} is an adjustable weighting factor, similar K_{rms} to and K_{ZVS} in (5). The selection of this factor is determined through an iterative process. $v_{k,EMI}$ represents the estimated cumulative EMI noise level, sensed as voltage at each port, as described in Sect. V.

V. EXPERIMENTAL PROTOTYPE

An experimental prototype has been developed with the parameters listed in Table I. The experimental prototype is

Fig. 8: TAB experimental prototype, parameters in Table I.

displayed in Fig. 8. To implement the cost function (5), an NI PXIe-1082 has been employed to oversample the HFT currents. The B-Box RCP (rapid control prototyping) is utilized to control the Imperix power modules and to execute the proposed MD-RCC. A power analyzer PW8001 by Hioki has been utilized to monitor TAB efficiency and losses.

Two sets of experiments are conducted to optimize the TAB ZVS operation with reduced rms current. Sect. V-A applies the approach outlined in Sect. III-A, using oversampling techniques to optimize the cost function in (5). While Sect. V-B presents an analog approach for estimating EMI noise levels optimizing the cost function in (7), as described in Sect. IV.

A. PXIe Oversampled Cost Function

Fig. 9 presents a schematic diagram of the experimental prototype in Fig. 8. The transformer currents i_1, i_2, i_3 are measured and sent to the PXIe-7862 FPGA, which oversamples the current measurements at approximately 2 MS/s, utilizing two ADCs for each current implementing the interleaving concept. In order to get synchronized measurements a digital signal from the B-Box is sent to the FPGA at the beginning of every switching cycle, fixing the acquisition window.

Given the switching frequency of the power switches at 40 kHz, around 50 samples are obtained per switching cycle. Fig. 10 compares the actual current waveforms measured by the oscilloscope with the samples recorded by the PXIe under various operating conditions for different ports. To detect the turning on instant, the Imperix B-Box sends a set of digital signals to the FPGA, representing the gating commands of the switches. All these data are sent using FIFOs to the PXIe-1082 chassis to be computed. Using both the oversampled waveforms of the transformer currents and the gating signals, the turn-on current for each switch per switching cycle, denoted as $I_{m,HS}$ and described in Sect. III-A by (5), is measured.

Since the oversampled current waveforms are recorded inside the PXIe, calculating the i^{rms} term described in (1) is feasible. However, this term can also be measured by other analog means, such as those described in [24].

Fig. 9: Schematic of the experimental prototype in Fig. 8.

Fig. 10: Matching transformer currents with oversampled current inside the PXIe at different ports and different operating cases. Preliminary test for the application of the approach in Sect. III-A.

To this end, the cost function I_{ZVS}^{rms} is computed within the PXIe and transmitted to the B-Box as an analog signal to perform MD-RCC optimization. To this end, the cost function I_{ZVS}^{rms} is computed within the PXIe and transmitted to the B-Box as an analog signal to perform MD-RCC optimization. As a final remark, the decoupling matrix used in Fig. 9 is identical to the one introduced in [14], which is primarily derived from fundamental component calculations.

B. EMI Noise Cost Function

Sect. V-A shows that an oversampling algorithm is required to measure online the cost function described in (5), adding complexity and cost to the setup. However, due to the

Fig. 11: Dynamic response of MD-RCC optimizing different cost functions [i^{rms} in (1), I_{ZVS}^{rms} in (5), and I_{EMI}^{rms} in (7)]: (a), (b), and (c) duty-cycles; (d) total rms current; (e) sum of hard switching current; (f) Cumulative EMI noise level.

correlation between the switch commutation current and the emitted EMI noise [27], which can be visualized in Fig. 11, an alternative cost function was proposed in Sect. IV.

A ferrite core is placed at each port of the TAB for sensing a signal representing the cumulative EMI noise of this port. The ferrite core functions as a transformer. The ferrite core utilizes the TAB dc port terminals as the primary winding, while the secondary winding is connected to a $50\ \Omega$ resistor, as shown in Fig. 9. An analog circuit then measures the rms voltage across the secondary winding, providing a correlation with the cumulative EMI noise. The EMI noise measurement circuit is an analog circuit that calculates the rms value, similar to the approach used in [24].

The rms calculator circuit is similar to the one described in [24]. This rms calculator, referred to as the EMI noise measuring circuit, produces v_k^{EMI} for each port, which is used in (8) to calculate v^{EMI} . The generated voltage is directly proportional to the EMI noise level and is utilized in the proposed cost function (7) in Sect. IV.

C. Experimental Results

To validate the performance of the proposed optimization, several operating conditions have been considered. Herein, a test case is shown at which power is transferred from port-1 to ports-2 and 3, with $V_1 = 400\ \text{V}$, $V_2 = 280\ \text{V}$, $V_3 = 320\ \text{V}$, $P_2 = 100\ \text{W}$, and $P_3 = 600\ \text{W}$. This test case is chosen at a low power level and with voltages mismatched to the

Fig. 12: Transformer voltage and current steady-state waveforms of the test case in Fig. 11: (a) PSM; (b) after MD-RCC optimizing i^{rms} (1); (c) after MD-RCC optimizing I_{ZVS}^{rms} (5); (d) after MD-RCC optimizing I_{EMI}^{rms} (7). As shown in (c) and (d), optimizing the proposed cost functions in (5) and (7), respectively, brings the TAB operation into a favorable zone with all switches having a soft turn-on transition and with almost the same rms current as optimizing rms in (1) solely.

transformer turns ratios to demonstrate the advantage of the proposed optimization in a relevant operating condition.

Fig. 11 shows the dynamic response of the proposed MD-RCC optimizing different cost functions (i^{rms} in (1), I_{ZVS}^{rms} in (5), and I_{EMI}^{rms} in (7)). Fig. 11(a), (b), and (c) show the optimization of the three degrees of freedom represented by the duty-cycles. The optimized duty cycles demonstrate that the converter can have different optimization points at various duty-cycles, which may result in nearly the same total rms current, as illustrated in Fig. 11(d). However, optimizing ZVS or EMI noise may slightly increase the total rms current.

Fig. 11(e) shows the sum of the hard-switching current as described in (6). Optimizing both cost functions in (5) and in (7) leads to zero hard-switching current, indicating full ZVS operation. However, optimizing only the total rms current in (1), does not account for ZVS operation, so the sum of hard-switching current does not by necessary reduce to zero. Fig. 11(f) shows the EMI noise level in (8). Optimizing I_{ZVS}^{rms} in (5) and I_{EMI}^{rms} in (7) result in lower EMI noise level compared to the optimization of i^{rms} in (1). Fig. 11(e) and (f) establish the correlation between the turn-on current of the switches and the EMI noise level.

Fig. 13: Transformer voltage and current steady-state waveforms of the test case in Fig. 11 with port-3 power increased from 600 W to 1500 W: (a) PSM; (b) after MD-RCC optimizing i^{rms} (1); (c) after MD-RCC optimizing I_{ZVS}^{rms} (5); (d) after MD-RCC optimizing I_{EMI}^{rms} (7). As shown in (c) and (d), optimizing the proposed cost functions in (5) and (7), respectively, brings the TAB operation into a favorable zone with all switches having a soft turn-on transition and with almost the same rms current as optimizing rms in (1) solely.

Fig. 12 shows the steady-state voltage and current waveforms of the HFT using PSM and MD-RCC on different cost functions with the same operating conditions described in Fig. 11. Fig. 12(a) shows the waveforms of PSM, where 8 switching devices have hard turn-on transition, indicated by red dots for ports-2 and 3. PSM records the highest rms current, EMI noise level and power losses. Fig. 12(b) shows the steady-state waveforms after optimizing i^{rms} (1), a reduction in the total rms current is evident. However, 4 switching devices remain in a hard turn-on transition,

as shown for port-2, and the EMI noise level is reduced compared to PSM. However, in Fig. 12(c) the steady-state waveforms after optimizing I_{ZVS}^{rms} (5) shows a reduction in the total rms current to a nearby value, with complete soft switching transitions achieved for the three active bridges of the converter. And with a noticeable reduction in the EMI noise level.

Fig. 12(d) shows the steady-state waveforms after optimizing I_{EMI}^{rms} (7). Herein, the number of hard turn-on devices is reduced to zero, with the lowest EMI noise level achieved.

Fig. 14: Radar graph comparing the performance of different modulation strategies: PSM, MD-RCC for i^{rms} , I_{ZVS}^{rms} , and I_{EMI}^{rms} . Key performance parameters include total rms current, total hard-switching current, EMI noise level, and power losses. The four parameters herein represent low performance of the converter at high values; hence, reducing these four values, lower graph area, is the aim of the proposed optimization. Notably, optimizing the proposed cost functions in (5) and (7) achieves the best solutions, which are marked by the lowest areas inside each graph, green and purple areas, respectively.

Fig. 13 shows the steady-state voltage and current waveforms of the HFT for a different operating condition, with port-3 power set to $P_3 = 1500W$, while maintaining the same voltage and power levels for the other ports as described in Fig. 11. Fig. 13 highlights the advantages of the proposed optimization, utilizing I_{ZVS}^{rms} and I_{EMI}^{rms} as cost functions for intermediate power levels.

To better assess the performance of the three cost functions compared to a benchmark modulation such as PSM, a radar graph is used in Fig. 14. In this figure, four key parameters are recorded for the steady-state operation of PSM, MD-RCC for i^{rms} , MD-RCC for I_{ZVS}^{rms} , and MD-RCC for I_{EMI}^{rms} . These recorded values include total rms current (1), total hard-switching current (6), EMI noise level (8), and total power losses. Reducing these four values enhances the TAB performance. This method provides a more comprehensive evaluation of converter performance, as the graph accounts for various factors, not just total losses. The radar graph is repeated for different loading conditions and with two voltage levels at port-3 while keeping the voltage and power levels at the other ports the same as in Fig. 11. A smaller area on the radar graph indicates better performance. Optimizing I_{EMI}^{rms} in (7) results in the best performance, as shown by the smallest

area highlighted in purple, followed by I_{ZVS}^{rms} in (5) with the green area, and then i^{rms} in (1) with orange area.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper demonstrates the feasibility of achieving a trade-off between zero voltage switching (ZVS) and reduced rms current in the triple active bridge (TAB) converter. Initially, a comprehensive grid search optimization (GSO) is conducted to identify the minimum rms current among points that achieve either partial or full ZVS. Following this, a multi-dimensional ripple correlation control (MD-RCC) method is employed to optimize a novel cost function that considers both rms current and hard-switching currents. An oversampling approach is used to acquire the proposed cost function online. A second cost function, based on cumulative EMI noise as a representative for hard-switching currents, is proposed for its simplicity compared to the oversampled approach. The results of the MD-RCC optimization highlight its advantages as an online, model-free, and adaptable method. While optimizing the new cost functions may yield points with slightly higher total rms current than the true minimum, the primary goal remains to balance total rms current with the hard-switching current. This trade-off not only enhances

efficiency but also impacts EMI noise levels and extends the converter lifetime. Experimental testing demonstrated the effectiveness of the proposed optimization using two cost functions. Total converter losses were reduced by about 42% and the sensed EMI noise by about 33% compared to PSM, while achieving full ZVS operation. These results show the effectiveness of the proposal to minimize losses, EMI noise, and hard switching. The main challenge is the need to use ferrite cores for sensing the common-mode generated EMI noise and the computational burden related to online optimization, which is limited thanks to the MD-RCC approach. Besides, the approach is model-free, therefore it is not critical in terms of knowledge of application details (e.g., parameters) for successful operation.

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